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Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR
NIMESULIDE IN BULK DRUG
AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY USING UV-
SPECTROPHOTOMETER****M. Bhaskar*, K. Kaveri, P. Shirisha, Asfiya, G. Sunitha and G. Shivakumar**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Smt. Sarojini Ramulamma college of pharmacy,
Mahabub nagar. T.G, India.**Abstract:**

A simple, rapid, accurate and economical UV-Spectrophotometric method developed for the estimation of Nimesulide from bulk drug and pharmaceutical formulations. The lambda max of Nimesulide in acetone and water was found to be 242 nm. The drug follows linearity in the concentration range 10-80 µg/ml with a correlation coefficient value of 0.9973, the proposed method was applied to pharmaceutical formulation and % amount of drug was estimated as 98.0%-102.00% and was found to be in good agreement with the label claim. The accuracy of the method was checked by recovery experiment performed at three different levels, i.e 80%, 100% and 120%. The % recovery was found to be in the range of 86.1%-89.03% w/w. The low values of % RSD are indicative of the accuracy and reproducibility of the method. The precision of the method was studied as an intra-day and inter-day variations. the % RSD value <2 indicates that the method is precise. CCCC

Keywords: Nimesulide pure and formulation, UV- spectrophotometer.

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INTRODUCTION:

Nimesulide is a relatively COX-2 selective, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) with analgesic and antipyretic properties. Its approved indications are the treatment of acute pain, the symptomatic treatment of osteoarthritis and primary dysmenorrhea in adolescents and adults above 12 years old, this medication is used to treat pain and dysmenorrhea (painful periods or menstrual cramps) *It is used to the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID).

Mechanism of action: Nimesulide is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that works primarily by Selectively inhibiting the enzyme cyclooxygenase 2 (COX 2). * Nimesulide is the result of its complete mode of action which targets a number of key mediators of the inflammatory process such as: COX-2 mediated prostaglandins, free radicals, proteolytic enzymes and histamine and rapidly absorbed following oral administration.

STRUCTURE :

Fig 1: Structure of Nimesulide

EXPERIMENTAL**Instruments and reagents**

UV- Visible Spectrophotometer Lab. INDIA analytical UV 3000, weighing balance of Contech, digital ultrasonicator of Nano Enterprise and all the chemicals used were of s.d Fine Chemicals and A.R. grade. Gift sample of Nimesulide was obtained from Qualichrome Labs. HYD, formulation was procured from local market a well-known brand of Nise tablets 100 mg manufactured by Dr..Reddys labs Pvt Ltd.

METHODOLOGY:**Preparation of Standard Stock solution**

Accurately weighed 100 mg of Nimesulide was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in 10 ml Acetone by shaking manually for 10 minutes and then sonicated for 10 minutes by the use of sonicator. The volume was adjusted up to the mark with the water as diluent to give the stock solution strength of 1000 µg/ml.

Preparation of working standard solution to get Standard Curve

Prepared serial working dilutions by using standard stock solution by pipetting 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.8 ml of solutions, were then transferred in to each of 10ml volumetric flasks, and were diluted to 10ml with diluent to get range of concentrations as 10-80µg/ml.

Preparation of Test solution

20 tablets of Nimesulide were taken and crushed well in a motor and pestle to get fine powder form and was taken weight equivalent to 10mg of this and was then transferred into a 10ml volumetric flask containing 10 ml of Acetone and then shaken well manually and was sonicated for 10 minutes and was filtered the volume was made up to the mark using the same solvent. Appropriate volume 0.1ml of this solution was pipette in to a 10 ml volumetric flask, and the volume was adjusted up to the mark using diluent. The resulting solution was scanned on a spectrophotometer for its sample absorbance measurements in the UV range 200-400 nm.

Table 1: Linearity Data

S.No.	Concentration	Absorbance
1.	10µg/ml	0.1092
2.	20µg/ml	0.2912
3.	30µg/ml	0.488
4.	40µg/ml	0.7280
5	80µg/ml	0.8625

Fig.2 : Linearity Graph showing concentration vs absorbance of Nimesulide

Table 2: NET Accuracy Data

S.No.	Percentages	Accuracy	Standard deviation (SD)	%RSD
1.	80% Accuracy	97.32%	0.001642	2.025
2.	100% Accuracy	98.57%	0.003214	2.141
3.	120% Accuracy	99.37%	0.0038	0.244

Table 3: Intra-Day Precision

Sample Name	Sample Absorbance	% Assay
Sample-1	0.3071	98.61
Sample-2	0.3074	99.32
Sample-3	0.3068	98.58
Sample-4	0.3073	98.70
Sample-5	0.3069	99.48
Sample-6	0.3071	98.61
Average	0.8703	99.88
% RSD		2.142

Inter-Day Precision

Table 4: Inter-Day Precision

Sample Name	Sample Absorbance	% Assay
Sample-1	0.3061	98.07
Sample-2	0.3064	98.25
Sample-3	0.3062	98.13
Sample-4	0.3067	98.56
Sample-5	0.3065	98.50
Sample-6	0.3060	98.01
Average	0.3063	98.25
%RSD		2.157

Table 5: Optical Characteristics Data for the proposed Uv- Method

S. No.	PARAMETERS	RESULTS
1	Absorption maximum (nm)	242 nm
2	Linearity range($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	10-80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Standard regression equation	$y=0.0247X +0.0514$
4	Slope	0.0247
5	Intercept	0.0514
6	Correlation coefficient	0.9973
7	Accuracy(% Recovery)	98.58 % -99.48 %
8	Precision (Intra-Day) %RSD (Inter-Day) %RSD	2.142- 2.157

CONCLUSION:

The above method was rapid tool for routine analysis of Nimesulide in the bulk drug and in the pharmaceutical dosage forms. The UV spectrophotometric techniques are quite simple, accurate, precise, reproducible and sensitive. The UV method and has been developed for quantification of Nimesulide in tablet formulation compared over pure drug. The validation procedure confirms that it is appropriate method for their quantification in the formulations. This method also used in routine quality control of the formulations containing their entire compound along with the other drugs or pharmaceutical excipients.

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REFERENCES:

1. B.K Sharma. Instrumental method of chemical Analysis. GOEL Publishing House, Meerut. 2022.
2. Y.R Sharma. Organic spectroscopy. S. Chand Publishing. 2007. Pp.356.
3. Kerrenth A. Connors. A Text Book of Pharmaceutical Analysis. Wiley, 1967; Pp 614.
4. A.I. Vogel .Vogel's Textbook of Qualitative chemical Analysis.
5. A.H. Beckett and J.B. Stenlake. Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry.
6. I.L. Finar. Organic Chemistry.
7. William Kemp. Organic spectroscopy
8. D.C. Garrett. Qualitative Analysis of Drugs
9. Qualitative Analysis of Drugs in Pharmaceutical Formulations. P.D Sethi Spectrophotometric identification of organic compounds Silverstein

10. P D Sethi. HPTLC. High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography: Quantitative Analysis of Pharmaceutical Formulations.
11. British Pharmacopoeia (HM stationary office, London, 2002), pg. no. 1216.